

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS 'INTEREST IN SUBJECTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Atamurodov Shodiyar Oralovich

JDPI. Docent of the faculty of Physical culture

Hasanov Anvar Toxirovich

JDPU Faculty of Physical Culture senior lecturer

Abstract: *The article reveals the importance of developing students of higher educational institutions of interest in subjects, the organization of their classes, the interaction of teachers and students, various technologies, methods, forms and means.*

Key words: *interest, independent work, opportunities, interactive methods, teachers, students.*

Аннотация: *В статье раскрывается значение развития у студентов высших учебных заведений интереса к предметам, организации их занятий, взаимодействия педагогов и учащихся, различных технологий, методов, форм и средств.*

Ключевые слова: *интерес, самостоятельная работа, возможности, интерактивные методы, учителя, студенты.*

Annotatsiya: *Maqolada oliy o'quv yurtlari talabalari o'rtasida fanlarga qiziqishni rivojlantirish, ularning darslarini tashkil etish, o'qituvchi va talabalarining o'zaro hamkorligi, turli texnologiyalar, usullar, shakl va vositalarning ahamiyati ochib berilgan.*

Tayanch so'zlar: *Qiziqish, mustaqil ish, imkoniyatlar, interfaol usullar, o'qituvchilar, talabalar.*

Self-education and self-education without the direct participation of the teacher the process of mastering the content of education is one of the main processes of the integrated pedagogical process. This is an example of this, especially since the percentage of independent work of students is growing from year to year.

Science does not stand in one place, it is constantly in development.

First of all, it is necessary to increase the interest of students in the sciences many scientists expressed their opinion about the concept of "interest".

Continuing this theme, D.V. Alexandrov writes in his definition of the concept of "interest" that the concept of "interest", like the concept of "need", reflects the practical state of necessity, but more meaningfully reflects the attitude of social actors to their existence and conditions of development.

The student learns conscientiously and independently when he is interested in himself, when he feels the need for it. O.S. Grebenyuk explains the conditions for the emergence of cognitive interest and consciousness: "It is important to pay attention in the pedagogical aspect," the ability to manage a person's motives, linking them to prospective goals comes to the fore.

If we look at the latest trends in education, it becomes clear that the primary role shifts from teacher to student. What "reader" means is an abbreviation of the phrase "self-teaching". It is possible to put a lot of effort into teaching, but there will be no result until the student accepts this teaching for himself.

That is why it is important to cultivate individual independence in the educational process.

According to Marchenko, "mastery is also the content of the subjects for which the main purpose of teaching is". "In the general definition, cognitive interest is the field of cognition, its objective aspect, and the chosen direction of the individual focused on the process of acquiring knowledge. Cognitive interest based on positive motivation brings the student to a state of success, a state of satisfaction with their activities. Therefore, the task of the teacher is to create these situations by organizing the learning process, to combine positive emotions from the learning process".

"How to increase teaching effectiveness?" - this is an age-old question of teachers. Gashenko S.A. In an article on the resources that increase the effectiveness of teaching at the institute, he notes the following:

1. more rational organization of teaching;
2. more appropriate organization of the learning material and the actions of students with it;
3. Wider use of students' "internal" resources (opportunities).

And if all this is not interesting to the student, then there will be no effect.

Therefore, as mentioned above, "internal resources" should include, first and foremost, an interest in and interest in education. With a purposeful and rational organization of the educational process, the answers to the question should never be forgotten: What is interesting for students?

"These questions were answered by conducting a survey among 2nd year students majoring in" Biology "of our institute." Why am I studying this specialty? "There were seven suggested answers to the questions. 51 students took part in the anonymous survey.

These results suggest that at any given time we may lose because 11.5% of students have the ability to lose. Other students need to further develop their cognitive interests and receive the necessary support from those interested in the learning process.

Encourage students to work together: by all students in the group, when the end result depends on each student. With such an organization of the developmental team, it is possible to take into account the interests and capabilities of each student, and sometimes to reveal hidden opportunities that the student has not previously identified.

"Interactive" methods, techniques are always accepted with interest by all students. As the development and implementation processes evolve, consultations, production meetings, and interim reports are held at points of particular importance to the system, that is, everything becomes as realistic as possible. In this way, students begin to understand what it means for everyone to contribute to the overall team work, and how its outcome will affect the overall outcome of the work.

Students who play the role of "leader" can have such a first experience. After defending the project, we need to analyze the whole process and each student individually and give each one a score based on their work and attitude towards it. Such organization of the educational process develops the ability and interest in learning, the profession, develops teamwork skills, increases responsibility for the assigned work, teaches students to listen to opinions, work with information independently, have the ability to make decisions and implement.

Students leave this project in a different way: more serious and from the real practical work entrusted to them.

As a project engineer, the teacher must constantly monitor and understand what is happening in the development team in production, provide timely methodological assistance to each student, avoid conflict situations, constantly communicate with students, and much more. Such an "interactive" method should definitely end with good results so that students can be proud of the work done. Under unusual "general" guidance, students should ultimately enjoy the results of their work.

In conclusion, motivating the student to learn as much as possible about their future profession is one of the specific goals of the institute as a whole and of each teacher. To this end, new technologies, methods, forms and techniques of teaching are being developed and applied. In addition, teachers are trying to identify new links

between a student's personality and upbringing, which is the responsibility of teaching him or her to effectively form the necessary knowledge and skills.

The interaction of teachers and students, different technologies, methods, forms and tools provide the necessary results in the learning process.

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